

A STUDY ON FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT (FDI) IN MULTINATIONAL RETAILING IN INDIA

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Abstract:

Globalization and liberalization brings lots of new innovative products to the world, FDI is the one among this, also there are number of different forms of FDI is available currently. Recently, Government of India allowed FDI in different sectors of Indian economy. Allowing FDI in multinational retailing has recently generated tremendous euphoria for some and fear for others. It is based on the notion that it will open floodgates for foreign retailers to invest and will change the retail landscape forever in India. The Government of India was forced to put on hold FDI in multinational retail but several political parties are making it a political issue in parliament on these policy decisions and amendments. Foreign Direct Investment in multi- brand retail will start a better integration of Indian economy into the global markets.

KEYWORDS: Foreign Direct Investment, MNCs, Retailers, Retail, Multi-brand, etc..,

INTRODUCTION

The G8 submit in which the countries such as Canada, France, Germany, Italy, Japan, Russia, UK and US were the fully developed countries. But to promote the developing countries the G20 submit was established and our country India was the member. After becoming the member of G20 submit, India allowed FDI sectors to invest in India by providing infrastructure and labour by this foreign companies come to India and invest in India in different sectors like retailing, industries, etc..,

The historical background of FDI in India can be traced back with the establishment of East India Company. After the Second World War, Japanese companies entered Indian market and enhanced their trade with India, yet UK remained the most dominant investor in India. Therefore, the Government adopted a liberal attitude by allowing more frequent equity participation to foreign enterprises and to accept equity capital in technical collaborations. It is during this period the government encouraged FDI,

allowing MNCs to operate in India. Thus, resulting in the partial liberalization of Indian economy. Indian retail industry is one of the sunrise sectors with huge growth potential. Economic liberalization in 1991 is the turning point of India. According to Reliance Retail Director Subramaniam V, the Indian retail market is one of the fastest growing in the world and is expected to reach USD 2 Trillion by 2032.

Foreign Direct Investment

Investment made by a company based in one country into the company based in another country is called Foreign Direct Investment. FDI is made in number of ways – either by setting up a subsidiary company in the host country by acquiring shares of the host country or through merger or joint venture.

The role of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in stimulating economic growth is one of the controversial issues in development literature. The great promise of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) by multinational corporations is that capital will stimulate dynamic growth. Beyond boosting income and employment, the hope is that manufacturing FDI will bring knowledge that indirectly effect in building skill and technological capacities of local firms, catalyzing broad based economic growth. The part played by FDI in the development process has undergone several changes. In the 1960's, FDI was seen in most countries as a partner in the development endeavors. India adopted a regime that was perceived to be restrictive towards FDI.

Retailing

Retailing is the largest component of the services sector in terms of contribution to GDP. Its massive share of 10-11% is double the figure of the next largest broad economic activity in the services sector. Retailing is the largest private sector in India and second to agriculture in employment. After farming, retailing is India's major occupation (8% of total population). It employs 40 million people.

The importance of retailing has become well-known in India only after 1991 when P.V. Narasimha Rao was the Prime Minister and Manmohan Singh was the Finance Minister.

As the part of economic liberalization process set in place by the industrial policy of 1991, the Indian government has opened the retail sector to FDI slowly through a series of steps:

- ❖ 1995 – World Trade Organization’s (WTO) General Agreement on Trade in Services (GATS) which included both wholesale and retail trade in services came into effect.
- ❖ 1997 – FDI in cash and carry (wholesale) allowed up to 100% under the government approval route.
- ❖ 2006 – FDI in single brand retail was permitted to the extent of 51%; FDI in cash and carry brought under automatic route.
- ❖ 2011 – 100% FDI in single brand retail permitted with government approval; 51% FDI in multi-brand retail with few conditions.
- ❖ 2020 – 100% FDI in single brand retail permitted under its automated route; 51% FDI in multi – brand retail under automated route with few strings attached.

What is Multi- Brand Retailing?

Multi-brand retailing refers to the marketing of the different unrelated competitive products under the same firm though being under the same firm, the various brands tend to bite into each other’s sales. For example, Pantaloons, Wal-Mart, etc. the multi-brand retailing has certain advantages which are as follows:

- ❖ Obtaining greater shelf space and leaving little for competitor’s product.
- ❖ Saturating a market by filling all price and quality gaps.
- ❖ Catering to brand-switching users who like to experiment with different brands.
- ❖ Keeping the firm’s managers on their toes by generating internal competition.

FDI in Multi-Brand Retailing

In 2008, the government contemplated opening up the retail sector and allowing 100% FDI in single- brand retail trading and 51% FDI in multi-brand retailing. However, it did not succeed due to fierce opposition from its allies and the left parties as well as the local trade association. AT Kearney the well -known international management consultancy, recently identified India as the ‘second most attractive retail destination’ globally from among thirty emergent markets. With the contribution of 14% to the national GDP and employing 7% of the total workforce in the country, the retail industry is

definitely one of the pillars of the Indian economy. India is largest among the Asian economies to liberalize its retail sector. Presently, global players are entering in India indirectly and allowing FDI is a great sign of buoyancy for retail purpose. India remains one of last frontiers of modern retailing.

Benefits of FDI in Multi- Brand Retailing

1. Improves social, cultural, political and economic standards.
2. Soaring inflation.
3. Industry experts feel allowing FDI will cut waste, as big players will build backend infrastructure.
4. FDI in multi- brand retail would also help narrow the current account deficit.
5. Moving away from intermediary – only benefits.
6. Job creation.

Benefits to Farmers

Farmers in India get only 10% - 12% of the price the consumer pays for the agri-products. Coming of organized retailing will benefit farmers in big way. Big retailers sell their product at very competitive prices. So, they source it directly from the farmers. Middle man does not have any place in this format of retailing. This will not only benefit farmers but also help in checking the food inflation. Also India has very inadequate facilities to store the food grains and vegetables. As the investment will flow into back end infrastructure, supply chain will get strengthened. Storage is a major problem area and 20% - 25% of the agri- products get wasted due to improper storage.

Challenges

Some of the challenges faced by the FDI multinational in retailing are as follows:

- Political scenario in the country.
- The competition from the Indian Multi – Brand retailers.
- Big retailers may become dominant and start having more bargaining power. So the profits gained by the farmers initially would close.

Conclusion

FDI in India has a significant role in the economic growth and development of India. FDI in India to various sectors can attain sustained economic growth and development through creation of jobs, expansion of existing manufacturing industries.

For the developing countries like India, FDI in multinational retail sector should be consciously considered by the Government of India. In broader way, India's local retail business will definitely get a chance for up gradation of the import of improved technological and transportation management knowledge from the multinational retail players. FDI in multinational retail will start a better integration of Indian economy into the global markets and, as such, it is important for the Government of India to develop retail sector for the total economic development of the country and welfare of society in the country. DI helps in the integration of cultural, social, political, and economic standards.

Reference:

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